

Review of E-Commerce Applications in Nigeria: Benefits and Challenges

**Muhammad Muhammad SULEIMAN¹, Surajo Musa YAKUBU²,
Safiyanu Sulaiman SALEH³, & Muhammad Nura Balarabe⁴**

¹School of Computer Application, Lovely Professional University, India

^{2,3}School of Management Studies

⁴School of Rural Technology and Entrepreneurship Development, Rano

^{2,3,4}Kano State Polytechnic, Nigeria

muhddkd@gmail.com, ORCID: (0000-0002-3646-3715)

Abstract

E-commerce is a profit-making transaction strategy that enables faster and wider business transactions in wider contexts of economic value and value creation via the Internet. The paper studies the current situation of e-commerce applications in Nigeria, with an emphasis on the drawbacks and advantages of online shopping in Nigeria. A review of the literature revealed that e-commerce applications have expanded dramatically over the years, creating a wealth of potential for both consumers and businesses. It also became clear that, despite the expansion, a number of challenges still prevent the business from reaching its full potential. Scarce infrastructure, weak legal enforcement, poor financial inclusion, a lack of access to technological advances, and a narrow selection of goods are a few of these barriers. Furthermore, research reveals that a lack of trust and knowledge is another factor impeding companies' and customers' adoption of e-commerce applications. Notwithstanding these obstacles, the country is working to advance e-commerce applications by expanding technological access, assisting small and medium-sized businesses, and encouraging cooperation between the public and private sectors. In conclusion, the study indicates that the Nigerian e-commerce market has sizable potential and that continuing attempts to address current issues may result in additional development and growth.

Keywords: *E-Commerce; E-Business; Government; Customer; Online Shopping*

1. Introduction

E-commerce seems to be a trend among businesses in this age of technology to help companies grow whenever and wherever they are. However, e-commerce is more well-known in terms of its concept than in terms of its application and reality. While many large corporations in our country have successfully adopted electronic commerce, other start-ups and small business organizations are reluctant to do the same, despite realizing its importance for both present and prospective commercial endeavours (Kit-Yeng Sin & Mun-Chong Sin, 2020), (Nabeel, 2007), (Ramón-Cardona et al., 2022).

Electronic commerce alone does not define e-commerce. It is an entirely new technique of managing a company through an instrument that modifies business rules. As a result, business management and strategy are far more crucial than technology (Lawal & Ogbu, 2015), (Das & Dress, 2022), (Attamah, 2019). E-commerce and E-business are sectors reliant on technology. An essential channel of communication between customers, sellers, and participants in the supply chain of goods and services has been made possible by the growth of the Internet and its commercialization through the World Wide Web. (Combe, 2006).

Businesses, governments, and local organizations or institutions have given electronic commerce or e-commerce, a lot of attention. A few convergent factors have been identified as the cause of this relevance. First among these is the expansion of the use of the net as a tool for communication and networking, as well as for the dissemination of

information. Secondly, the widespread adoption of open standards in computer software applications and the affordability of personal computers have both enhanced their computational power. The third is a supporting legal framework where the government and regulatory agencies work together on a larger scale to ensure that e-commerce laws, policies, and regulations are upheld for the protection of consumers, Wong & Sculli cited in (Said, Mohamed Ahmed Azizan, 2016). The government of Malaysia launched the "Malaysia Broadband Initiative" this year to promote high-speed broadband access. As a result, Malaysians will be able to browse the Internet at speeds ranging from 5 Mbps to 20 Mbps Faulkner et al. cited in (Said, Mohamed Ahmed Azizan, 2016), (Shemi, 2016), (Abtahi, Ahanaf Tahmid Farhana, Nazia Hassan, 2023), (Kit-Yeng Sin & Mun-Chong Sin, 2020).

Typically, Two branches of electronic commerce can be identified. These are listed below:

- a) Electronic Finance, credit cards, debit cards, smart cards, ATMs, mobile banking, online banking, insurance, and mortgages are all included in electronic finance (Okolie & Ojomo, 2020), (Lawal & Ogbu, 2015).
- b) E-Merchandise: Selling goods and services online and transferring them through distribution channels, like in the case of online purchases of groceries, tickets, music, apparel, hardware, travel, books, flowers, and presents (Okolie & Ojomo, 2020), (Lawal & Ogbu, 2015), (Shemi, 2016), (Das & Dress, 2022).

2. Conceptual Framework

E-business and e-commerce are two different ideas, though they are frequently used interchangeably. As stated by (Andam, 2003), E-commerce and information and communication technology are employed in business-to-consumer transactions as well as inter-business and inter-organizational transactions (transactions between and among organizations). On the other side, with e-business, ICT is applied to improve one's business. Any procedure carried out by a commercial organization—profit, nonprofit, or government—over a computer-mediated network is included. "The transformation of an organization's processes to deliver additional customer value through the application of technologies, philosophies, and computing paradigm of the new economy" is a more comprehensive definition of e-business" (Ibrahim & Abubakar, 2015:2) (Okolie & Ojomo, 2020), (Abtahi, Ahanaf Tahmid Farhana, Nazia Hassan, 2023), (Plane, 2019).

According to Till cited in (Okolie & Ojomo, 2020), the term "e-commerce" any form of ICT-based business, administration, or information sharing is referred to by this term. E-commerce, as defined by the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD), is a new way of doing business that relies on non-proprietary protocols and networks with open standards, such as the Internet. E-commerce is what Kinder refers to cited in (Okolie & Ojomo, 2020), It also refers to search, evaluation, and transaction systems or processes, as well as post-transaction interactions, that are created and maintained for commercial gain. E-commerce refers to the use of digital data processing and electronic communications in commercial activities to establish, alter, and define relationships that add value between or among businesses as well as between those organizations and individuals (Andam, 2003).

According to (Lawal & Ogbu, 2015), e-commerce involves companies using contemporary communication tools such the phone, fax, internet, e-payment, money transfer systems, and e-data exchange (Okolie & Ojomo, 2020), (Kit-Yeng Sin & Mun-Chong Sin, 2020).

3. Electronic Commerce Development in Nigeria

Even while e-commerce is growing in popularity worldwide, underdeveloped countries like Nigeria seem to be lagging behind. Nigeria is a developing country where ICT is booming, with 16.1% of the population having access to the Internet (Internet World Stats, 2009) (Lawal & Ogbu, 2015).

Despite these worries, Nigerians have mainly accepted the use of e-banking and payment systems, which is one aspect of e-commerce. Nigerians prefer digital banking over physical banking because it gives them quicker and more convenient access to financial services (such as money transfers between accounts, online access to bank statements, and bill payments for utilities like electricity and water). However, these customers are susceptible to a variety of cybercrimes when making transactions online (Egwali, 2009). Poor telecommunications facilities, erratic electric supply, inferior payment methods, and inadequate security have all hampered the growth of e-commerce operations like Internet banking in Nigeria Ayo et al cited in (Lawal & Ogbu, 2015). The majority of people are discouraged by all of the aforementioned challenges from fully embracing and utilizing e-commerce, which prevents the development of e-commerce in Nigeria. These factors can also be seen as environmental factors that have an impact on the people being studied in this particular setting (Nigeria) (Lawal & Ogbu, 2015).

E-commerce has its roots in the 1948 Berlin airlift when messages were sent electronically. After that, it transitioned to what was then known as Electronic Data Interchange (EDI). Together, many industry groups developed the electronic data that was used for their transactions in transportation and commerce. The EDI system was first utilized to conduct online business in the development of the Internet, but its operating costs were greater due to the need for a private network. Because of this, only a few very large corporations were able to run it, and they had to provide financing to help smaller businesses adopt and use the EDI system. However unlike today, e-commerce has been defined by the advent of the Internet, and many businesses are utilizing it (Rabiu et al., 2019).

In light of the importance attached to electronic commerce, the federal government of Nigeria, through its various agencies, developed a number of institutional arrangements to sanitize the financial sector of the country's economy, stem the tide of fraudulent activities in the country, and rein in bank financial malpractice. The following are some of the major actions taken by the Nigerian government to promote the expansion of e-commerce in Nigeria:

a) **Legislative Efforts:** A few of the regulatory measures the Nigerian government implemented to purge the financial sector of the economy include the Independent Corrupt Practices Commission (ICPC) Act of 1999, the National Drug Law Enforcement Agency (NDLEA) Act of 1989, the Money Laundering Act of 1995, and the Failed Bank (Recovery of Debt and Financial Malpractice of Banks) Act of 1994. They were set up to stop the growth of fraud across the country. Other institutions designed to address the fraud issue include the Economic and Financial Crimes Commission (EFCC) and the National Cyber Crime Working Group

(NCWG) (Lawal & Ogbu, 2015). As part of the attempts to stem the flood of fraudulent practices in the nation's financial institutions, a Nigerian IT solutions service provider is currently collaborating with SAS of South Africa to provide an anti-money laundering solution for institutions. 2006; Chibuez cited in (Lawal & Ogbu, 2015), (Okolie & Ojomo, 2020).

b) **On-going ICT Projects:** These include the mobile internet units (MIUs) and the WIN program. The mobile internet Units are used to offer ICT education to rural areas and include businesses with ICT amenities such as personal PCs, VSATs, and auxiliary devices. WIN is the product of the "Wire Nigeria" initiative. Its goal was to provide ICT infrastructure across the country. In order to complete the project, the required infrastructure, principally a fibre optic backbone across the country, must be installed. Additionally, VSATs must be made available to all 774 local government areas in the country (Lawal & Ogbu, 2015), (Okolie & Ojomo, 2020).

c) **National Policy for Information:** A plan developed in 2000 is to blame for the industry's enormous expansion. Establishing Nigeria as a pioneer in the information age and an IT-capable country in Africa is the aim. Its main objective is to "Use IT" for a variety of goals, such as agriculture, job creation, government, wealth creation, healthcare, and the eradication of poverty (Lawal & Ogbu, 2015) quote (Ajayi, 2005). But in 2006, it was highlighted that Nigeria had Africa's fastest rate of telecom growth. According to Iroegbu, e-commerce in Nigeria was expected to have earned around N75 billion in 2012, and if that growth rate continues, we could be looking at N160 billion in another four or five years cited in (Okolie & Ojomo, 2020).

4. Defining E-Commerce

By gaining market share, electronic commerce has become hailed as an affordable means of reaching clients around the world (Tan et al., 2007) (Agwu & Murray, 2015). In its simplest form, electronic commerce refers to transactions that occur remotely as opposed to on paper. Sending product orders and invoicing over a network is an illustration of electronic commerce. 2002's Bandyo-Padhyay cited in (Kelvin, 2020). E-commerce is the application of ICT to facilitate exchanges and transactions amongst a business and its customers, collaborators, suppliers, stockholders, and other parties, Currie cited in (Kelvin, 2020), (Ranjan, Kumar Ravi Singh, 2022).

Electronic commerce encompasses all of the services and information from pre-purchase information to post-purchase service and support, in addition to email and other communication channels, that a business may provide to its customers over the Internet. Essentially, e-commerce has two main applications. The first is to use technology to reduce transaction costs by improving the way you use your time and procedures. As an alternative, you might utilize it as a marketing tool to increase sales (and customer service) and to create new enterprises, such as contact centres, software support services, and information technology-enabled businesses. Thus, it serves as a tool to promote ongoing operations and a chance for new business, for both established businesses and new competitors. Consumers can conduct banking transactions, investments, purchases, distribution, communications, exploration, and study from almost anywhere with an Internet connection (Lawal & Ogbu, 2015), (Agwu & Murray, 2015).

E-commerce is defined as the trade of goods and services via the Internet, a sizable

network of personal computers. It is also known as the process of trading products and services, as well as buying, selling, and transferring information via the Internet. The field of technological advancement that is constantly changing is e-commerce (Rabiu et al., 2019), (Abtahi, Ahanaf Tahmid Farhana, Nazia Hassan, 2023), (Said, Mohamed Ahmed Azizan, 2016).

5. Characteristics of Electronic Commerce

Below are some characteristics of e-commerce;

- i. **Ubiquity:** e-commerce is always accessible and available everywhere. Because customers can shop whenever they want and from any location using PCs, laptops, tablets, and phones, online stores never close. For customers, this lowers transaction costs (Kelvin, 2020).
- ii. **Universal Reach:** Compared to conventional commerce, electronic commerce is much more efficient and practical because it enables business transactions to span cultural and national boundaries. Both demographic and geographic barriers can be overcome through electronic trade (Kelvin, 2020).
- iii. **Universal Rules:** The internet norm, which is utilized for e-commerce activity, is the only set of technology standards that every country in the world adheres to (Kelvin, 2020).
- iv. **Interactivity:** It is how e-commerce technology functions. Because users may engage with the material, there is a two-way interaction between the merchant and the customer (Kelvin, 2020).
- v. **Data richness:** Information density is dramatically increased via the internet. This is the complete and precise data that

is available to all market participants, including buyers and sellers. The complexity and depth of the communication are simply referred to as rich communication (Kelvin, 2020).

- vi. **Customization:** Electronic commerce enables personalization and customisation by enabling businesses to target particular persons or groups with their promotional materials. Using their names, past purchase histories, and areas of interest, advertising and items are customized for specific people or groups based on their preferences (Kelvin, 2020).

6. Types of Electronic Commerce Transaction

Depending on how the parties deal with one another, electronic commerce can be categorized. The classifications are as follows (Kelvin, 2020);

- 1) **Business-to-Business (B2B):** Using the intranets, extranets, internet or personal networks, two organizations conduct business. This form of transaction could happen between a company and the companies that make up its supply chain, and between a company, the government, and any other company. Any entity, private or public, for-profit or non-profit, is considered an enterprise in this setting Turban et al. cited in (Ranjan, Kumar Ravi Singh, 2022).

A supermarket and its vendors serve as an example. Google is a fantastic illustration of a business that engages in this type of transaction. Business-to-business transactions make up the full wholesale transaction. Dell purchases all of its components online and sells its goods to organizations and businesses online. In this sort of e-commerce, all of the players are either companies or other

companies Turban et al. cited in (Ranjan, Kumar Ravi Singh, 2022).

- 2) **Business-to-Customer (B2C):** Clients can order goods and services, have them delivered digitally or physically, and pay for them using electronic funds and secure payment methods. Through electronic publishing, consumers can also learn more about products or services (Agwu & Murray, 2015), (Ranjan, Kumar Ravi Singh, 2022).
- 3) **Business-to-Government (B2G):** This sort of online connection is when corporations provide government and non-government groups with input (Agwu & Murray, 2015).
- 4) **Government-to-Citizen (G2C):** A form of online interaction in which a government body offers its citizens and other players access to national transactions, such as local government services, information about the federal government, and tax information (Agwu & Murray, 2015), (Ranjan, Kumar Ravi Singh, 2022).
- 5) **Consumer-to-Business (C2B):** This category includes both individuals and businesses that use the internet to advertise their goods and services to other businesses and look for sellers to compete for their business. Priceline.com organizes consumer-to-business travelling service deals (Agwu & Murray, 2015), (Ranjan, Kumar Ravi Singh, 2022).
- 6) **Consumer-to-Consumer (C2C):** Business dealings between consumers fall beneath this group of activities. The eBay auction sales, in which consumers list their products for other consumers to bid on and purchase, are an example of consumer-to-consumer electronic commerce. Another illustration is the promotion of private companies online

and the purchase of knowledge and abilities on the net (Agwu & Murray, 2015).

7. Benefits of Electronic Commerce

The adoption of electronic commerce is influenced by its capacity to bring value to firms and by people's awareness of potential benefits. According to Salnoske cited in (Lawal & Ogbu, 2015), (Attamah, 2019). Below are some benefits of e-commerce in Nigeria;

- i) **Efficiency of Cost Reduction:** E-commerce is the most capable and efficient way to launch, grow, and operate a business. Its operational costs are lower than those of conventional businesses. These expenses include the cost of starting the firm, the cost of operating it, the cost of logistics, the cost of materials, and the cost of distribution, sales, and promotion (Attamah, 2019).
- ii) **Market Advantage:** Ecommerce gives enterprises more access to the worldwide market and a larger reach. E-commerce provides a significant amount of awareness, visibility, and potential for the promotion of services and products. Additionally, e-commerce raises customer market awareness, which encourages competition and lower prices. Once more, e-commerce improves customer service, brand recognition, order taking, and processing, all of which promote high levels of consumer loyalty (Attamah, 2019).
- iii) **Increased Efficiency:** With the help of electronic commerce, companies may operate with a high degree of efficiency in several areas, such as managing their supply chains, which reduces transaction costs for labor, overhead, inventory, sales, and transaction processing. Additionally, e-commerce aids companies in enhancing

transaction speed, quality, and accuracy (Attamah, 2019).

- iv) **A Competitive Edge:** When used effectively, Businesses gain a competitive advantage through electronic trade, which increases profitability. This strengthens the market position of companies in the industry (Attamah, 2019).

8. Challenges Facing Electronic Commerce in Nigeria

Nigerian Business-to-Consumer electronic commerce is growing in popularity and participation as the nation's internet usage rises and new B2C businesses keep popping up, but this industry continues to encounter several obstacles. The future of B2C e-commerce in the nation is being hampered by difficulties like insufficient internet facilities, lack of widely accepted payment methods, security concerns, and the expense of using the net, difficulty with shipment, difficulties with confidence, and many more factors. The following issues are taken into account;

- i) Poor internet facilities high access fees and other infrastructure-related issues. Everywhere in the globe, successful business-to-consumer e-commerce depends on a strong net infrastructure; if this goal is not met, e-commerce will suffer because the internet is its primary conduit. Customers may easily access information, do thorough product searches and comparisons, and quickly, conveniently, and affordably assess the offerings of numerous businesses thanks to the internet, Bagdoniene & Zemblyte cited in (Kelvin, 2020).
- ii) The absence of a common payment technique a globally recognized form of settlement is required for the efficient operation of electronic commerce, particularly B2C E-commerce. Its absence becomes problematic. According to

Aminu cited in (Kelvin, 2020), the lack of a well-developed electronic payment system in Nigeria deters people from shopping online (Kelvin, 2020).

- iii) Trust It has been said that consumer adoption of electronic commerce may be hindered by an absence of trust in web vendors. Mckenzie et al. cited in (Kelvin, 2020). Sharing private information such as postal addresses and phone numbers, business data, such as inventory data, and financial data, such as credit card details, is frequently necessary for digital transactions among parties to the transaction (Kelvin, 2020).
- iv) Lack of enjoyment: Unlike traditional retail establishments, online purchasing includes only A computer and the client. The common feelings of pleasure, diversity of things, and abundance of sights to take in are non-existent. As a result, online purchasing cannot be a replacement for these experiences (Agwu & Murray, 2015).
- v) Issues to find things: Rose et al. made it abundantly evident that some customers have trouble locating certain items they want to buy, which results in poor page accessibility (Agwu & Murray, 2015).

Advantages of ECommerce

The following are e-commerce's benefits and drawbacks.

For Businesses

- Improved Revenue
- Cheap Promotion
- Little Barriers to Entry

For Consumers

- Price Drops

- International Marketplace
- Availability round-the-clock

DISADVANTAGES OF E-COMMERCE

For the Business

- Website maintenance
- Software and hardware
- Cost of implementation
- Training and upkeep
- Website stickiness and customer loyalty

For the Consumer

- Inability to personally inspect products
- Online shopping security

9. Conclusion

The potential of electronic commerce is being embraced by a growing number of businesses and organizations in Nigeria; nonetheless, a number of critical challenges must be solved before e-commerce can be profitable in Nigeria. It is clear that problems like inadequate ICT infrastructure, subpar telecommunications networks, a lack of awareness of e-business, an inadequate legal and regulatory framework, high internet service costs, partially automated banks, privacy and security concerns, mistrust, internet service costs, and logistics need to be identified, understood, and improved. The Nigerian government must therefore begin taking action to hasten the adoption of e-commerce, which would promote economic growth in all states.

10. Recommendations

The conclusion drawn from this study is that for e-commerce to be effectively implemented, several factors must be considered, including the following:

- 1) To establish efficient business operations between customers and suppliers via the Internet, an organization must keep up with the pace of technology. Rebuilding IT infrastructures and information architectures is necessary.
- 2) Policy steps are required to lower the high cost of internet access and assure network security to encourage greater acceptance of e-commerce among private organizations. (Michael, J. 2010) cited in (Said, Mohamed Ahmed Azizan, 2016).
- 3) The structure of the company must be completely altered to accommodate e-commerce. All organizations transitioning to digital must think about restructuring their entire company or perhaps starting a new one, as well as putting new management practices into place, making changes to their corporate culture, and adopting new staff methods of management. They will need to rethink their entire business strategy in addition to developing a new framework for information systems and networked processing operations (Chaffy, 2002; Laudon and Traver, 2003) cited in (Said, Mohamed Ahmed Azizan, 2016).
- 4) Online companies must create a robust IT infrastructure to coordinate their online transactions, business activities, and any potential linkages with competitors in their industry. Electronic companies must, however, choose the Internet technology that best fits their operations and data architecture. Many types of software and hardware components can be employed for various commercial applications. As a result, the

company must select the appropriate technology for its information technology system (Said, Mohamed Ahmed Azizan, 2016). In addition, technology is continually evolving and introducing new gadgets, applications, and systems.

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